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VISUALS: AN INTERACTIVE WEB APPLICATION TO ASSESS RESULTS OF A 6600 SQ KM LANDSCAPE SURVEY IN CHERKASY OBLAST, UKRAINE

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VISUALS: ІНТЕРАКТИВНИЙ ВЕБЗАСТОСУНОК ДЛЯ ОЦІНКИ РЕЗУЛЬТАТІВ ЛАНДШАФТНОГО ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ПЛОЩЕЮ 6600 КМ² У ЧЕРКАСЬКІЙ ОБЛАСТІ, УКРАЇНА

To encourage use of data collected during a survey from satellite sources of 6600 sq km of the Cherkasy oblast, we offer a guide to using our results in an interactive web application. This contribution notes the options available in that app and gives examples of possible uses that may be posed to answer questions regarding archaeological landscapes in this part of Ukraine. We hope that will encourage local archaeologists to try it for themselves.

Keywords: Satellite, survey, Cherkasy oblast, web app, VISUALS, archaeological landscapes.

З метою заохочення використання даних, зібраних під час дослідження 6600 км² території Черкаської обл. на супутникових джерелах, ми підготували посібник щодо застосування отриманих результатів в інтерактивному вебзастосунку. У посібнику описано доступні функції застосунку та наведено приклади можливих сценаріїв використання, що можуть слугувати для розв'язання питань, пов'язаних з археологічними ландшафтами цього регіону. Ми сподіваємося, що це заохотить місцевих археологів до самостійної роботи з даними.

Ключові слова: супутник, розвідка, Черкаська обл., вебзастосунок, VISUALS, археологічні ландшафти.

Introduction

VISUALS is an interactive web app, designed and constructed by M. Fowler using publicly available software, to enable unlimited open access to data collected during a three-year archaeological survey over part of Ukraine (Palmer et al., 2023). Parts of this area had been studied previously using traditional archaeological field methods. Of relevance to our use of satellites is K. V. Shyshkin's aerial photography research in the 1960s and 1970s which identified the majority of the Trypillia culture megasites in and beyond the present area (Шишкін, 1973, 1985) (see also *Trypillia sites* below). A partial comparison of the locations of the sites we identified with previously known archaeological sites was also one of the tasks of our study (see *Known sites in Talnivskii environs* below).

Data for our survey were collected through interpretation of Google Earth satellite images (2007–2022) plus five strips of declassified HEXAGON photographs taken on 18 May 1982.

Results were cross-checked against historic maps, mostly within the Google Earth platform. To make the mixture of data into a useable single source, M. Fowler created an Excel workbook (named FROGLET) that successfully combined the different data sources and tools into a consistent workflow of data recording for the project (Fowler, 2022). From there, the finalised database was then incorporated into an ArcGIS Online map and the web app created as an ArcGIS Instant App (ArcGIS, 2025). After testing and use by the writers, the app was named VISUALS – a name derived from ‘Visualising the Interpretation of a Satellite-based Ukraine Archaeological Landscape Survey’ or, in short, ‘Visualising Ukraine’s archaeological landscape from satellite data’. Both summarise its purpose and scope. This note provides a guide to the functionality of VISUALS and gives some suggestions on ways for its use in archaeological research.

The survey covered an area of 110 by 60 km, mainly located in Cherkasy oblast and identified over 10000 sites. Zooming facilitates interrogation of

individual sites and study of areas of interest. In VISUALS, sites are shown as predominantly point data, but also as lines or polygons where appropriate. By clicking on a data point, it can be interrogated to see a version of the original Google Earth database entry that includes our unique number, coordinates and site type plus a qualitative guide to the certainty of the interpretation and its present-day condition. The majority of sites identified are in heavily cultivated land and are visible as soil or crop colour differences. The database also includes the image dates on which that site was identified and additional descriptive comments written by the interpreters to as objectively as possible describe what was observed. Each record includes the initials of at least two interpreters to show the origin of the data and its quality control. The first indicates the person who carried out the initial interpretation of the site and the following documents who carried out the review for quality control ensuring consistency. This checking process could and did lead to the alteration of the description of sites, changes in confidence of interpretation or lead to identification of additional sites or reassignment to a different site type after discussion with the original interpreter.

After a brief note about GIS use within archaeology, this contribution is mostly a guide to the uses of VISUALS, the layers within it, and some brief case studies to indicate how it may be applied to study the archaeological landscapes it records. More detailed archaeological information and explanations can be found in the two project reports (Palmer et al., 2023, 2025).

Advantages and problems with using Geographic Information Systems

Since the 1980s, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have become essential in archaeological projects that use spatial data and they are the core of heritage management systems in many countries. A recent review of worldwide peer-reviewed publications shows the range of uses that have been made of GIS by archaeologists and provides a historiography (Menéndez-Marsh et al., 2023).

We will expand on that work to include recent use of GIS in Ukraine, which has been applied at local and country-wide scale. Examples of 'local' use come from the work of V. Hnera and colleagues to store and process data from field surveys which they see as the beginning of a national archaeology map (Гнера et al., 2023). Perhaps more relevant to the

scale of our survey (itself covering only 1% of Ukraine) are the efforts of K. Polyvach to create an E-Atlas of Ukraine's cultural landscape about which they have published a series of papers (Поливач, 2024). The E-Atlas is a way of storing, systemising and visualising information about a relatively small number of sites that are on UNESCO's World Heritage List for the purposes of cultural landscape conservation. In so doing, this follows practices established in other European countries. However, to add a site to a GIS requires knowledge of its precise location and boundaries and K. Polyvach noted that the past absence of cartographical data makes this problematic (Поливач, 2024, с. 139). Our project, which begins with geographically located sites, has found similar problems when attempting to compare our sites with those from published or archival sources in which, for example, the location of a mound or surface scatter of artefacts may have a location recorded as 'three fields north of the village'. Even if that location can be suggested by visual examination of satellite images or maps, it is rarely of sufficient precision to link an image-derived feature with field information. Similar problems occur in those countries where maps and aerial photographs were, or still are, regarded as sensitive.

VISUALS includes standard GIS tools such as separation of layers, simple measurement and profiling terrain. A lot of valuable archaeological research can be done with these basic tools to study sites, their context and relationships with other natural and anthropogenic sites. At a later date, all data will be uploaded to Zenodo from where it can be copied by others and used in a more analytical GIS environment.

The web app, VISUALS

What follows begins with a general description of available functions in VISUALS after which is a detailed review of features and layers within the app, how to find them and what the controls allow. Lastly is a series of case studies that use VISUALS to examine elementary archaeological questions that may be asked of fairly extensive territories or of local sites and their environments.

We recommend reading the first part with VISUALS open in a computer so that items can be operated and checked. As the site is under development some layers may be moved in later versions. We also note that updates by Esri to their Instant Apps can change the design and layout of VISUALS. The text below was correct for the

version in use on 28 October 2025. The link for the latest version of VISUALS is available through the Ukraine Working Group page of the Aerial Archaeology Research Group (<https://aargonline.com/wp/working-groups/ukraine-wg/>).

Description of data layers within VISUALS

Various categories and types of data produced during the project are available for display using the layer list. This includes the project results from aerial interpretation as well as supporting layers which can be useful for interrogating the data within VISUALS.

Project results include the following categories: *Archaeology*, *Non-Archaeology*, *20th Century features* and *Trypillia sites*. The supporting layers include negative areas along with maps showing the *World Shaded Relief* and *Soil types*. In addition, a layer called ‘Known sites in Talmivskii environs’ documents known archaeological sites from publicly accessible databases as well as from archival material. These layers will be discussed below.

Project results layers

Project results can be divided into archaeological and non-archaeological types. This note includes an explanation to justify the inclusion of the non-archaeological and 20th Century content. Post-depositional changes can impact the visibility of earlier archaeological remains and thus the reliability and integrity of our knowledge of their structure and distribution.

Archaeological features.

Archaeological features here refers to both prehistoric and historic sites which include mounds, habitation sites, hillforts, enclosures, field systems and others. They have been discussed in project publications (Palmer et al., 2023).

Non-archaeology.

This category documents features, either natural, or other artefacts (modern agricultural or image-based) that on certain images could be confused with archaeology. After examining all the data sources these features have been considered doubtful as having an archaeological origin. They were described within the GE database with reference to the feature they could be mistaken for but appended ‘n/a’ (not applicable) to indicate the lack of confidence in their likelihood of being archaeology. Examples of this are hollows which often appear as circular features which can look similar to ploughed-out mounds on some 2D images.

Likewise, some river deposits can appear similar to habitation sites. These interpreted features are included to show the audit trail of their interpretation on the images and information available at the time of the project. These interpretations may change with additional information.

All examination of aerial/satellite images is subjective and experience and comparative examples will help any future work with images here and in similar geographical contexts. In addition, these non-archaeological features can be a useful teaching aid and will be valuable as input for training Artificial Intelligence models.

20th century features.

Features or sites from the 20th Century include collective farms, fuel stores, abandoned villages, shrunken villages, Cold War sites and various infrastructure. It is probable that some of the 20th Century features will themselves be considered ‘archaeology’ at some point in the future.

Collective farms were recorded in this project because in the span of image dates (1982 to the late 2010s, or beyond) the buildings associated with collective farms changed from operating systems to abandoned and, in places, destroyed. The majority of land parcels linked to the collective farms now remains unused and overgrown. Collective farm buildings are also recorded on the 1:10,000 Soviet map dated to the mid-1970s. Similarly, the fuel stores (so named on the Soviet map and probably associated with the collective farms) were functioning in 1982 but most were later abandoned. Inclusion of these in our database helps explain modern landuse and also identifies places where damage to earlier archaeological features may have occurred. These abandoned sites may also be mistaken for earlier archaeology.

Abandoned and/or shrunken villages were added to the database because of their rapid change from ‘in use’ in 1982 (with some shown and named on the Soviet map) to abandoned during the span of Google Earth images available at the time of the project. In places, whole villages have been abandoned in the relatively recent past. In some cases, abandonment follows the damming of adjacent rivers that may have caused localised flooding or unacceptable damp conditions. Examples of the so-called shrunken village, in which sometimes one part of a larger town has become disused, may be due to cessation of activity at a nearby collective farm or industrial site. These abandoned and shrunken villages become negative areas that may cover or

mask earlier sites. They may also become of interest to archaeologists and historians in their own right (see Case study 3 below).

Cold War sites include constructions for missile launching and their support complexes recorded when active in 1982. Since then they have been dismantled but traces remain visible in later images. Investigation of Cold War remains has become an accepted theme for some archaeologists in, for example, Poland and Britain at a time when there remains the possibility to obtain first-hand accounts through documenting memories of people who were there during the use of those sites (Kiarszys, 2024).

Other recent infrastructure and constructions may also have damaged earlier archaeological features and several types of these are shown. Layers within VISUALS include roads, railways that were formerly functioning but have since become disused and in cases buried or removed. There are also buried pipelines, of which some are also shown on the Soviet map (c.1975) and former factories or utilities that, for example, were for processing mineral extraction. Any of these may have impacted earlier archaeological features.

Supporting layers

Supporting layers are provided which can be used alongside the project results to understand the distribution of sites and aid in landscape analysis. These include project grid tiles and lettering, a World shade relief map, soil maps and layers which collectively form negative areas.

Negative areas.

These are defined in this project as those that preclude the identification of archaeological sites that are obscured by overhead canopy as well as areas of the ground which may have been significantly disturbed. As such they play an important role in distinguishing areas that may be devoid of archaeology from those where human activity is undetectable using aerial photograph and satellite image interpretation. Negative areas are included because they may have covered and/or potentially destroyed possible archaeological features and should be taken into account when analysing causes or gaps in areal distribution. The negative areas identified in this project include built up areas, woodland and bodies of water. They were digitised from available data and added as individual layers.

Built-up areas may have partially or completely destroyed surface archaeological information in the process of their construction, remodelling and use.

There may remain small archaeological features (such as a mound) in small plots of land but there is little chance of convincingly identifying these from satellite images.

Woodland may preserve upstanding archaeological features but can mask their visibility on conventional images. As such woodlands are regarded as negative areas in this project. However, this may change when airborne laser scanning (ALS or lidar) data becomes available as it can be processed to 'see through' woodland and record the micro-topography within it (Bennett et al., 2025).

Non-archaeological features mentioned above in *20th Century features* which have altered and disturbed the landscape, namely collective farms, Cold War sites, abandoned or shrunken villages, mineral extraction and buried recent infrastructure can all be considered as negative areas when analysing older archaeology.

Drainage, including lakes or broader rivers which result from modern damming may cover archaeological features which may be revealed when water levels are lower. Bodies of water and selected rivers are shown on both base maps and are included in VISUALS as a separate layer.

Additional archaeological content comes from two projects by Working Group members:

Known sites in Talnivskii environs. Data in this layer was compiled by O. Kariaka and shows information resulting from historical fieldwork that is now accessible in two sources: unpublished archive literature (settlements only) and a publicly available Ministry of Culture database (sanctuaries, settlements, mounds, hillforts and burials/burial grounds).

Comparison of this information with that collected from interpretation of satellite images proved difficult for two main reasons. Archival collections frequently used weak location descriptions rather than location coordinates and frequently used a single point to indicate more than one feature on the ground, especially when recording groups of mounds. This makes it problematic to reliably compare the archival collections with data from image interpretation and thus provides scope for further work.

Trypillia sites. Data relating to Trypillia sites results from a search through published literature and databases conducted by V. Ward. The aim was to specifically identify their locations in order to understand how they appeared on satellite images and to use this information to identify new or

additional sites. An issue with documented location confidence quickly became apparent; a significant number of sites in the database created by M. Nebbia (2018) were assigned low values of Location Certainty for their geographical coordinates. As a result of this project, many of the sites were located with confidence on the satellite images and therefore their location certainty was upgraded. Trypillia layers in VISUALS reflect the auditable changes and updates to site locations as discovered as part of this project. Colour coding shows the status of those sites after examination of satellite data for this project. A solid green point was confirmed, hollow green gives the likely location, blue shows possible new sites. Not all of the listed sites could be confirmed on the available satellite images as some images had been collected on dates when archaeological information was not visible. Alternative locations have been suggested for several of these when sites that matched earlier descriptions were identified nearby (dark magenta). Light magenta is also used for two sites that could not be confirmed from image examination. A single site uses a yellow square to mark an unlikely location for a Trypillia site although other habitation has been suggested nearby.

Grid lettering and **the Sentinel-2 tile (10km grid)** remain from the initial design of the project survey. The grid numbering is a legacy which reflects the initial project proposal to interpret an area equivalent to a Sentinel-2 tile. The truncation in the square numbering results from the initial proposal to survey this larger area which included an additional six rows to the north. The area was reduced as a result of the large volume of sites being identified and the stringent requirement to quality control the identification and documentation of the sites across multiple data sources. Site IDs in the database are based on those squares, eg A06_001 is the first site identified in square A06.

Soil types. Two maps of soil types are included. One shows just two soil types derived from the ArcGIS online layer *Soil Types in Ukraine* based on the Harmonized World Soil Database (Nachtergaele et al., 2023). The other is a georectified version of the 1:2,500,000 soil map of Ukraine published by the General Directorate of Surveying and Cartography of the Soviet Ministry, GUGK, SSSR in 1977. This is subdivided into seven general soil types that can be selected individually. More-detailed and larger-scale soil maps may help explain why archaeological sites were constructed where they are/or why they have survived on certain soils. This knowledge also can

have value in describing negative areas or those in which features may not be easily visible from above.

World Shaded Relief from ArcGIS Online provides an alternative background map (used in Figures 6 and 7 below) without the distraction of boundaries, names and modern roads.

Sketch layer is a new addition made by Esri for which we have identified no function (28 October 2025).

Guide to the interactive web app

The interactive web app, VISUALS, enables project results to be displayed in a variety of categories. This enables a user to examine them as a total or partial distribution against a choice of background information. This section attempts to explain basic uses before a sample of archaeological questions that can be asked of VISUALS are described in section 4.0.

- The opening interactive screen (Fig. 1) shows the study area with a 10km grid and its lettering outside the study area boundary along with the *Project results-Archaeology layer* displayed as colour-coded point and polygon locations. Zooming to a different scale can be done using the + or – buttons at the top right corner or via a mouse wheel. The circled ‘i’ at the right of the VISUALS header opens a brief written overview of the survey and interactive map and shares links to the project reports.

In the upper left corner of the screen area are seven buttons (Fig. 2) whose names can be seen by hovering the cursor above each. These are explained from top to bottom as follows:

- **Default map view** resets the initial overview if zooming in has been used.
- **Layer List** gives access to all the layers described above. Individual layers or sub-categories can be toggled on or off in the viewer.
- **Legend** shows the point colour and shape used on the map for each layer and sub-category.
- **Bookmarks** resets an overview if zooming has been used.
- **Search** enables searching by word or site number or through any word that has been used in the database comments (e.g. satellite). Use of the small triangle on the left lets a user select a specific layer in which to search or to search in all layers. The current version opens a single database entry and highlights the symbol on the map.
- **Reset map orientation** realigns the map to match that of the original Sentinel 2 tile on which the

Fig. 1. The opening interactive screen of VISUALS that includes archaeological data as colour-coded points and polygons

Fig. 2. Named interactive buttons in the upper left of the screen as current on 28 October 2025

project area was based. The original alignment and overview can be regained by clicking the Default map view button or Bookmarks.

- **Toggle Basemap.** The large icon at the bottom switches background from the default map to an undated satellite overview. An additional map can be opened in Layer view – see below).

Using the Layer List

Features in the Layer list are shown in Figure 3. The default display map will have All archaeological features already turned on.

Most layers can be expanded and each can be turned on or off i.e. made visible or not using the ‘eye’ button.

The interpreted features which comprise the project results are shown in two ways, either as points only, or as points with an associated line or polygon. All point data are shown as colour-coded symbols. By right clicking on the symbol a database entry will open that includes our interpretation and the image sources. Features that cover a larger area or are linear are additionally shown as polygons or lines in VISUALS. Clicking on the polygon and line symbols opens an abbreviated database.

At the lowest level in the features list there is the additional option to display a table. This table provides the database contents for the points visible on the screen viewer at that time. If this is selected at the opening default map view, the table will display 7639 entries from the *Project results – Archaeology*

Fig. 3. Layer list at its opening level. Layers with > can be expanded. This is the crucial button for manipulating and visualising the contents of the map

layer. By zooming in, these numbers will reduce to reflect what is then visible in the screen display.

Clicking on a point displays the record for only that point which is itself highlighted. More than one point can be selected for display in the table. The table can be closed when it is no longer wanted.

It should be noted that the 10 km grid and its letter-number identification shows the basis of our working method in which we identified and pinned features within each square. This resulted in sites

being named by square and sequence, for example, D08_022. This naming convention also allows the user to locate sites relatively quickly to a 10 x 10 km geographical area.

Archaeological content includes two layers that were mentioned in the Introduction: known sites in the Talnivskii environs and a merged database of several that list Trypillia megasites.

Some layers may contain similar or duplicate information. As the list layers are stacked it may be necessary to turn off the Habitation layers in *Project results – Archaeology* and *Archaeology – Lines and polygons* in order to read information regarding the Trypillia database.

Background maps can be changed. Clicking *toggle basemap* provides satellite views (undated) that change images as you zoom in. Alternatively, the *World Shaded Relief* button opens a background that shows topography and rivers. Roads are superimposed if satellite is selected from the *toggle basemap* option below the button bar. Other useful background maps to display and interrogate are the soil map and the various negative areas displays.

There is a button added by Esri, *Sketch layer*, for which we have identified no function (as at 28 October 2025).

Buttons at the upper right of the screen provide standard functions such as are familiar from use of other programs (Fig. 4). The top button opens the Language switcher and gives the option of Ukrainian or English on the buttons of the app. Note, however, that the text in the database remains in English if Ukrainian is selected.

Fig. 4. Buttons in the screen's upper right

The print button offers a range of options that include page size and orientation with the option to save in pdf (default), jpg or png32 format. There are options to set scale and write headers, etc, but note that at present, only pdf format shows point data and none include a key / legend. Use of the bottom button, Export to pdf, saves a view plus a legend for point data but omits the legend if lines and polygons are turned on. Enter fullscreen enables full screen display – and returns it to window view when clicked again. The + and – buttons change the zoom value of the area view and Use of the Share panel copies what is currently open on screen, including any popups, and saves it to clipboard as a web link.

Buttons along the bottom right of the screen provide some potentially useful functions (Fig. 5). From left to right in there is first an elevation profile feature. Users can draw a line on screen and the corresponding elevation profile is displayed below. Moving the cursor along the profile shows its location on the map (although this cannot be screen saved). The second button opens an overview map that outlines the area of the interactive map that is open on screen.

The third button (that shows a pencil) expands to give a selection of drawing tools that include point, line, polygon and circle and may be very useful for simple annotations. The fourth button enables measurement of length and area as well as showing coordinates (in a range of values) at the pointer. The fifth button opens the ‘Welcome’ page of VISUALS.

Fig. 5. Buttons at bottom right of screen

Case studies that use VISUALS for archaeological purposes

Examples of how to interrogate the project results data using VISUALS are outlined below but users are encouraged to ask their own research questions and play with the combinations of evidence.

Case study 1: Suggesting territorial boundaries

The archaeological point and polygon sites in squares C07, C08, D07 and D08 are shown in Figure 6 below. The background map is the World Shaded Relief over which watercourses mostly have been marked by a single line. A steep-sided river cuts

across the area from approximately North-West to South-East. The distribution pattern of mounds (orange) suggests this may have been a territorial boundary during the time of their building as those to its North show planned lines that extend along ridges, while those to the South are less structured. Other topographical information such as elevation, slope, soil type, and negative areas can also be interrogated to assess their potential relationships with the mound distributions.

Case study 2: Relationship between field systems and settlements

Magenta polygons showing the occurrence of possible prehistoric field systems in square H08 underlay point features (mounds) as well as additional points and polygons representing habitation (Fig. 7). Of interest, are the relationships between individual mounds within the field systems and the presence of habitation sites (identified as closely-spaced groups of mounds and shown using a blue symbol) close to the Western edge of the Northern field system. Close relationships between fields and settlements are known from elsewhere in Europe and this may be a Ukrainian example.

Case study 3: Disturbed Ground

As well as opening in the general ‘non-archaeology’ layer, certain features such as collective farms have separate layers in the 20th century layer (Fig. 8). An example of this can be seen at Myzynivka where a collective farm, now demolished but partly visible as vegetation patches, overlays part of the earlier hillfort. Construction and use of the collective farm along with field boundaries and road are likely to have caused damage to the hillfort. Figure 8 indicates this association and has highlighted the blue database point of the farm which opens the table (partly shown) on the right side of the figure. The background satellite image shows the hillfort’s banks and ditches but higher-level interpretation and mapping would be required to effectively assess the likely damage caused by construction of the collective farm.

Case study 4: Elevation profile tool

The elevation profile tool can be seen at the bottom of the screen in Figure 8 but is here (Fig. 9) covered by the profile. It can be used to create an elevation profile along a drawn line and is shown here with exaggerated height. In this example at Myzynivka, this type of display can be helpful to

Fig. 6. Squares C07, C08, D07 and D08 with different patterns of mound distribution over World Shaded Relief plus Drainage

Fig. 7. Mounds (orange), suggested field systems (magenta) and areas of habitation (blue) in square H08 on a background of World Shaded Relief

Fig. 8. Point data indicates the remains of a former collective farm (highlighted blue triangle) which earlier satellite images showed to partly overlay the South-East part of a hillfort (red square) which is itself visible in the background satellite image taken in 2018. By clicking on the collective farm symbol, project data about it is displayed and can be scrolled down for more information. This can be done for any symbol. The proximity of the scatter of mounds (yellow) to the South of the hillfort raises questions about contemporaneity which fieldwork may answer.

Fig. 9. An example of using Elevation profile tool. An elevation profile (with exaggerated height) at Myzynivka cuts across the location of a cluster of mounds (arrowed) and shows them to be situated on a natural terrace

Fig. 10. An area around Talne showing negative zones (built-up areas and woodland), archaeological point data and all 20th century features as points, lines and polygons. Note the absence (almost) of earlier archaeological features within the negative zones. Background is the default map

understand the relationship of the group of mounds to the local topography. In this example, an arrow has been added to Figure 9 to indicate where this linear group of mounds occupy level ground just East of a slope down to a watercourse.

Case study 5: Using negative areas

A map extract below shows an area around the town of Talne (Fig. 10). It includes layers of negative zones including built-up areas (grey polygons), woodland (green polygons), 20th century features that include mineral extraction (black diamonds), collective farms (blue triangle) and a Cold War SAM site (black triangle). Along with line data, for example the pipeline crossing the South of the figure, the negative area polygons give an indication of the extent of land within which archaeological features are unlikely to be recorded on satellite images. These negative areas help understand gaps in the distribution of archaeological information.

Conclusions

Work in other countries has demonstrated that interpretation of satellite images and aerial photographs (where these are available) can reveal details within archaeological landscapes as well as in smaller scale survey. Our project in Cherkasy oblast may be the first step to do similar work throughout a small part of Ukraine. The web app, VISUALS, was designed to allow interactive use of results from that survey and to combine different types of information in the quest to formulate and perhaps answer archaeological questions. The above description of VISUALS's operations along with several case studies may encourage its use by Ukrainian archaeologists who have an interest in landscape studies.

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